

COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING PRACTICES IN INDIA AND IMPROVEMENT STRATEGIES

Pediatrics

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ABSTRACT

Proper nutrition is essential in the first two years of life to sustain the rapid growth which occurs in this period otherwise it can lead to malnutrition. Appropriate complementary feeding practices are important, as malnutrition in this phase of life can affect the developmental process and also increase the risk of adulthood metabolic diseases. The present article is aimed to discuss the complementary feeding practices in India, determinants influencing it and strategies for improving it. The recent data was collected and analyzed from Pubmed, MedLine and Google Scholar. The timely initiation of complementary feeding varied widely across the country (42.7-84%). There were limited studies on the adequacy of complementary feeding. Many factors which influenced complementary feeding practices were identified and can be utilized in formulating intervention programs. Interventional studies showed nutrition counselling of mothers is beneficial. Strengthening public nutrition programs require micro-planning, focusing on local factors, motivated healthcare staff and continuous monitoring. Culturally acceptable, economical and locally available cuisine of nutritionally rich complementary food need to be developed and the skills of hygienic preparation and responsive feeding should be imparted to mothers.

KEYWORDS

Infant And Young Child Feeding, Malnutrition, Health Education, Responsive Feeding

INTRODUCTION

According to World Health Organization (WHO), malnutrition refers to deficiencies, excess or imbalance of nutrients. (1) About one-third of the under-five mortality is directly or indirectly, attributed to undernutrition. (2) Majority of children in developing countries, who live below the poverty line and face deprivation and starvation have delayed physical and mental development. Environmental factors like socio-economic status, parental attitudes, hygiene and child rearing practices affect the nutritional status of children. (3)

According to NFHS-4, 31% of children under 5 years of age were stunted in India as compared to 48% in NFHS-3. The percentage of under-five children found underweight and wasted in NFHS-4 were 29.1% and 20% respectively, as compared to 42.5% and 19.8% respectively in NFHS-3. (4,5) Over the period of 10 years, there has been a remarkable reduction of 17% in stunting and 13.4% in underweight, but the percentage of wasted children remain the same.

Complementary feeding is defined as the systematic process of introduction of semi-solid food at the right time in addition to mother's milk in order to provide needed nutrients to the infants. (3) Indian infants receive complementary food, but either they are introduced too early or too late. Dietary diversity is not maintained and minimum number of feeds are also not given. The age of initiation of complementary food was 3 to 5 months in the urban upper and middle income groups while in the urban lower income group it was delayed by 7 to 9 months and in rural areas by 9 to 11 months. (6)

According to NFHS-3, 52.6% children were being introduced complementary feeds along with continued breastfeeding at age of 6 to 8 months, and this remained stagnant in NFHS-4 at 50.1%. NFHS-4 also looked into the adequacy of complementary feeding and found only 11.6% of children between 6 to 23 months were receiving an adequate diet. (4,5)

Child feeding practices have a wide spectrum and they need frequent changes during the initial years of life. (2)

The present article discusses complementary feeding practices in India, determinants influencing it and strategies for improving it.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The information was collected from Pubmed, MedLine and Google Scholar. The keywords used for the search included: *malnutrition, complementary feeding, under-five children, infant and young child feeding, India*. The search since 2010 until date yielded 49 articles out of which 13 articles, which were not related to the topic were excluded. Eleven articles were analyzed under the section problem burden, 15 articles on the timing of initiation, 15 articles under determinants, 5 articles under starter food used, 6 articles under adequacy of complementary feeding and remaining under the headings of introduction, discussion, and health interventions. These were critically reviewed, analyzed and the information is presented.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

Complementary feeding is defined as the process starting when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of infants, and therefore other foods and liquids are needed, along with breast milk. (7)

Introduction of solid, semi-solid or soft foods: Proportion of infants 6–8 months of age who receive solid, semi-solid or soft foods. (2)

Minimum dietary diversity (MDD): Proportion of children 6–23 months of age who receive foods from 4 or more food groups. (2)

The 7 food groups are:

- Grains, roots and tubers
- Legumes and nuts
- Dairy products (milk, yogurt, cheese)
- Flesh foods (meat, fish, poultry and liver/organ meats)
- Eggs
- Vitamin-A rich fruits and vegetables
- Other fruits and vegetables.

Minimum meal frequency (MMF): Proportion of breastfed and non-breastfed children 6–23 months of age, who receive solid, semi-solid, or soft foods (but also including milk feeds for non-breastfed children) the minimum number of times or more. (2)

- For breastfed children, minimum is defined as 2 times for infants 6–8 months and 3 times for children 9–23 months.
- For non-breastfed children, minimum is defined as 4 times for children 6–23 months.

Minimum acceptable diet (MAD): Proportion of children 6–23 months of age who receive a minimum acceptable diet (apart from breast milk). (2)

- For breastfed children 6–23 months of age who had at least the minimum dietary diversity and the minimum meal frequency during the previous day.
- For non-breastfed children 6–23 months of age who received at least 2 milk feedings and had at least the minimum dietary diversity not including milk feeds and the minimum meal frequency during the previous day.

PROBLEM BURDEN

The undernutrition status reported by various studies from different parts of India revealed that among the under-five children, 34.3% to 54.4% were under-weight, 24% to 58.7% were stunted and 16.9% to 35% were wasted. (Table 1) The wide range of observational differences may be accounted because of the varied methodology used like the selected study age group, sample size, study indices and operational definitions, and also because of the regional customs and traditions of the study region.

Table 1. Prevalence of malnutrition among under-five in India

Location	Study year	Sample size	Age group	Malnutrition Prevalence (%)
India, NFHS-3 (5)	2005-06	Multi-centric	Under 5 years	Underweight- 43 Stunting- 48 Wasting- 20
India, NFHS-4 (4)	2015-16	Multi-centric	Under 5 years	Underweight- 36 Stunting- 38 Wasting- 21
Rohtak, Haryana (8)	2019	600	1-5 years	Underweight- 54.4 Stunting- 41.3
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh (9)	2018	256	6-23 months	Underweight- 38 Stunting- 24 Wasting- 35
Rural areas of Madhya Pradesh (10)	2015	5457	0-12 months	Underweight- 41 Stunting- 29 Wasting- 33
Pune, Maharashtra (11)	2014	658	Under 5 years	Underweight- 34.3 Stunting- 58.7 Wasting- 16.9
Central Karnataka (12)	2013	100	9-12 months	Stunting- 32 Wasting- 34
Bareilly, Uttar Pradesh (13)	2012	166	Under 5 years	Underweight- 66.3
Andhra Pradesh (14)	2011	805	Under 3 years	Underweight- 39 Stunting- 30 Wasting- 22
North Bihar (15)	2011	1405	6-59 months	Acute malnutrition- 15.4
Chandigarh (16)	2011	803	0-5 years	Underweight- 50.4

TIMING OF INTRODUCTION OF COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING

The National Family Health Survey-4 shows a dismal decline in timely introduction of complementary feeding, from 52.6% (NFHS-3) to 42.7% in 6-8 months old children. (4,5) Studies across India have found different proportion of children being timely introduced to complementary feeding: in Kolhapur district of Maharashtra, 62.5% at 6 months (22), in Bangalore district of Karnataka, 64.5% at 6 months (18), in Amlapuram district of Andhra Pradesh, 42% at 6-7 months (19), in Dehradun district of Uttarakhand, 70.1% at 7-9 months (20), in Tumkur district of Karnataka, 55% at 7-9 months (12), in Medak district of Andhra Pradesh, 58% at 6-11 months (23) in Mangalore district of Karnataka, 77.5% at 6 months (24), in rural districts of Madhya Pradesh, 57% at 6-11 months (10) in Bankura district of West Bengal, 55.7% at 6-8 months (25) in Lucknow district of Uttar Pradesh, 69% at 6 months (9), in Bhopal district of Madhya Pradesh, 84% at 6-8 months (26), in Udupi and Dakshina Kannada district of Karnataka, 77.5% at 6 months (27), in Loni district of Maharashtra, 84% after 6 months (28). The wide variations can be attributed to the

local practices of the areas studied and difference in the study population characteristics (place of residence (urban/rural), age group, socioeconomic status and maternal education).

STARTER FOOD USED FOR INITIATING

The consistency of starter foods given to infants was thin as compared to the semi-solid consistency recommended. (2) Various studies showed that dal water, rice water, biscuits mixed in milk, animal milk, khichadi and fruit juices were used as starter foods. (9,21,22,23,24)

ADEQUACY OF COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING

Only few studies have looked in the adequacy of complementary feeding by studying the Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) indicators on minimum diversity, frequency and acceptability of diet. (2) NFHS-3 does not categorically mention the IYCF indicators as they were defined five years later in 2010. But it categorizes 6 to 23 months children in:

1. Breastfed group: consuming three or more food groups (36%), fed minimum number of times (43.7%) and both consuming 3+ food groups and minimum number of times (22.1%)

2. Non-Breastfed group: consuming milk or milk products (81.7%), consuming four or more food groups (31.1%), fed minimum number of times (26.6%) and fed with three IYCF practices (11.9%)

The NFHS-4 studied the indicators and revealed that Minimal Dietary Diversity, Minimum Meal Frequency and Minimum Acceptable Diet in the breastfed children was 20%, 31% and 6.7% respectively while for the non-breastfed children 34%, 61% and 14% respectively. (4) MDD, MMF and MAD was reported at Bhopal (26) as 57%, 86% and 58% respectively, at Aligarh (29) as 42.6%, 50.9% and 35.6% respectively and at Bankura (30) reported 24.4%, 67.0% and 31.5% respectively. A study at Lucknow found in the breastfed children MDD, MMF and MAD to be 59.8%, 60.1% and 43% respectively while for the non-breastfed children it was 59.8%, 69.4% and 61.2% respectively.(9)

Higher number of children receiving MDD, MMF and MAD reported in the studies from Bhopal and Lucknow as compared to NFHS-4 may be due to the fact that their study population comprised of mothers having higher education, 73% and 57.4% respectively, as compared to the national average of 35.7%.

DETERMINANTS OF COMPLEMENTARY FEEDING PRACTICES

The different determinants that impact the complementary feeding practices have been studied by various researchers, which are presented in Table 2.

The vast number of influencers suggest that strategic planning needs to be done at micro-level, keeping the local factors in mind while planning an Interventional Program. Not only social, economic and educational factors but traditional beliefs and myths also need to be addresses.

Table 2. Determinants of Complementary feeding practices

Factors having negative impact	Factors having positive impact
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maternal perception of not having enough milk • (Early initiation of CF) (20,21,17) • Maternal perception of having milk enough for child's needs (Delayed initiation of CF) (17,27) • Pre-lacteal feeding (28) • Use of commercial foods (14,17,18,20,23,27) • Bottle feeding (24,25,26,27) • No use of separate feeding utensils for child (17) • Not allowing child to self-feed (23) • Feeding by other family members (21) • Faulty advices of family members (17,20,24,27) • Working Mothers (18,26) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional birth (27) • Exclusive Breastfeeding (14) • Nutrition advice during health visits (17,27) • Parental education (9,26) • Urban residence (29) • First child (27) • Nuclear family (17,26) • High socioeconomic status (27) • Non-working mothers (18,26) • Male Sex (29)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vomiting/ diarrhea on initiation of CF (19,20,27) • Illness (21) • Food myths/ misconceptions/ customs (19,21,28) 	
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CF= Complementary Feeding

HEALTH EDUCATION INTERVENTIONS

Interventions directed towards education of the mothers on initiating and continuing appropriate and adequate complementary feeding, better hygiene and child caring practices, may effectively prevent malnutrition. An interventional study at Belagavi found that food diversity, food consistency, food quantity, meal frequency and modes of feeding complementary food were improved after following health education intervention to mothers. (32) A study at Chandigarh utilized nutrition educational intervention and digitized child undernutrition tracking module for health workers to improve complementary feeding. It found that significantly higher number of infants in the intervention group were started on complementary feeding at six months of age and received foods having thick consistency. There was significant weight and length gain in them. Community involvement in programs make them more sustainable. (33)

A study in urban slums of Delhi found the impact of the educational intervention directed through peer counselors to promote optimal complementary feeding practices. In the intervention groups, which included one sub-group counselled by nutrition professional and the other two by the peer-counselors, the prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding at 6 months, complementary feeding beyond six months and children receiving breast milk till the age of 12 months were higher. The positive change in practices were nearly similar in groups counselled by the nutrition professional and the peer counsellors. (34) Community-based health education intervention on the awareness level of mothers, has been proved to be effective even in malnourished children, in a study done at Puducherry. There was an increase in protein intake, calories intake, and weight gain in the intervention group. This also brings into focus that not only the provision of complementary feeding but also the awareness on appropriate complementary feeding practices is important to prevent malnutrition. (35)

Responsive feeding, whereby the mother feeds her child in response to child cues and psychomotor abilities, has gained interest in the establishment of developmentally appropriate feeding. (7) Responsive feeding intervention showed significant improvements in children's self-feeding and mother's verbal responsiveness. (36) Researchers in Andhra Pradesh followed 600 mother-child dyad for a 15 months period who were randomized into three groups, the control group (CG) who received routine Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS); the complementary feeding group (CFG) who received the ICDS plus the WHO recommendations on breastfeeding and complementary foods; and the responsive complementary feeding and play group (RCF&PG) who received the same intervention as the CFG plus skills for responsive feeding and psychosocial stimulation. The results showed that community based educational interventions can improve dietary intake, length (CFG) and mental development (RCF&PG) for children under 2 years. (37)

An important facet of child nutrition is availability of mother for feeding. The working mothers are entitled to 26 weeks maternity leave under Maternity Benefit (Amendment) Act, 2017, which covers the period of exclusive breastfeeding but beyond that, in the critical phase of complementary feeding introduction they are forced to leave their infants to be cared by other family members or domestic help. (38) A study in Delhi on working mothers showed that longer maternity leave, higher income, and utilization of counselling services facilitated adoption of optimal feeding behaviour. (39) The working status of the mother has been shown to be negatively impacting the complementary feeding practices, so reforms are needed to enable them to be with their infant as long as possible, in the form of work from home, crèche facility at workplace and shorter work hours.

DISCUSSION

Addressing the nutrition gap requires identification of the magnitude of the problem of incorrect feeding practices among the care givers of children below 2 years. Prenatal nutrition in the mother's womb and nutrition in the first 2 years of life account for the first 1000 days of critical nutrition, which has an everlasting impact on the child's

neurodevelopment and lifelong mental health. The programming of many future health risks, including obesity, hypertension, and diabetes, are dependent on nutritional status during this period. (40)

The World Health Organization studied healthy populations of children from birth to 5 years of age from the USA, Brazil, Norway, Ghana, Oman and India, in the Multicenter Growth Reference Study (MGRS), and found that the differences in the growth of children at different sites were inconsistent, small, and biologically unimportant. (41) Thus in the first 1000 days the growth potential in different ethnicities is similar under optimal health, nutritional, and environmental conditions (42)

Various national programs like Integrated Child Development Service (ICDS); National Health Mission; Reproductive and Child Health Programs; Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child and Adolescent Health (RMNCH+A) Strategy and Poshan Abhiyan are formulated with components for improving the nutritional status of the country. At the grass root level, Anganwadi workers and Accredited Social Health Activists (ASHA) are the key persons to deliver services to target groups. All programs have a special emphasis on promotion of exclusive breastfeeding for six months and then addition of complementary feeding thereafter. India celebrates September as National Nutrition Month and it emphasizes the promotion of quality nutrition, including micronutrients. Success of such programs depends on meticulous planning based on regional statistics, capacity building of healthcare staff, growth monitoring, supply of hygienic and quality nutrition supplements, continuous monitoring and continued information, education and communication (IEC) activities. Favorable results are subject to a multitude of factors including local requirements, traditions, community acceptance, food security, food beliefs or myths, child rearing practices and cooking facilities.

Optimal nutrition depends of multiple factors including literacy, purchasing power, family size, quality of food, hygiene, food beliefs and myths, socioeconomic status and psychological wellbeing. It was found that not only factors associated with socioeconomic inequality but feeding practices, health-care seeking behaviour and the mother's nutritional status are associated with malnutrition. (43) The developing world is facing the problem of rapid population growth and limited availability of resources which indirectly affects the nutrition status of the population. Hence, for long term results strong political commitment of socioeconomic development with food security is needed.

RECOMMENDATION

It is recommended that optimal IYCF education imparted to mothers right from the time of pregnancy, which can bring a change in attitude and practice towards exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months and then beyond six months nutritionally acceptable complementary feeding in conjunction with continued breastfeeding till the first two years of life. In a country where only 54.9% babies are exclusively breastfed and only 42.7% are started timely complementary feeding, we have a large scope of improvement. Mothers should be imparted with the skills of preparation of low-cost high-energy foodstuff which is culturally acceptable. Strengthening public health interventions for providing nutritional education of complementary feeding which is timely, diverse, in appropriate frequency and fed hygienically and practicing responsive feeding is the need of the hour, as the adequacy of the complementary food should also be now the focus of the program.

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